

Study of a Friction Modulation Haptic Interface Based on Thin-film AlN Actuators

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Abstract. This paper presents the study of a low-voltage haptic interface developed at CEA LETI based on friction reduction through ultrasonic actuation. The system is driven by $2\ \mu\text{m}$ thick AlN piezoelectric actuators deposited on glass and exploits the resonance of a Lamb mode at $f = 67.2\text{kHz}$. A laser Doppler vibrometer characterisation, a tribological study and a psychophysical campaign have shown that the system is efficient for voltages below $50\ V_{pp}$.

Keywords: Friction reduction · Ultrasonic actuation · Piezoelectricity · Lamb mode

1 Introduction

Haptic interfaces are developing and opening up new ways of communication through the sense of touch. We decided to construct a haptic touch interface with varying levels of friction. We chose to build a haptic touch interface with friction variation through ultrasonic actuation [1–4]. To actuate our haptic system, thin film piezoelectric aluminium nitride (AlN) actuators were used with the aim of creating an easy-to-use haptic demonstrator that highlights the integration possibilities of such actuators while using a low actuation voltage. This paper presents for the first time the proof of concept of a haptic effect generated by thin film actuators made through tribology measurements and a psychophysical campaign.

2 Design

The device consists of a free $140.91\ \text{mm} \times 87.73\ \text{mm}$ and $500\ \mu\text{m}$ thick glass plate (Corning eagle XG) and four $2.9\ \text{mm} \times 81.63\ \text{mm}$ and $2\ \mu\text{m}$ thick AlN transducers (Fig. 1a). Electrodes made of molybdenum are located below and above the AlN layer. Our aim is to modulate the friction reduction effect at a frequency that is sensitive to the finger to create a variety of interesting textural effects.

3 Characterisation

A Laser Doppler Vibrometer measurement was carried out (Fig.2a) and a displacement amplitude of $300\ \text{nm}$ was obtained for $50\ V_{pp}$. This value, quite low compared to

Fig. 1: a) Photograph of the system. A support part external to the haptic system is visible ; b) Lamb's anti-symmetric 28-node mode. Position of actuators is indicated by red arrows.

Fig. 2: a) Voltage/Displacement characteristic at resonant frequency in a maximum amplitude point ; b) Friction coefficient over time, modulated at frequency $f_{mod} = 10Hz$

the guidelines usually given by the literature, is compensated by the high actuation frequency of $67.2 kHz$ [5, 6].

A tribological measurement was carried out, using a 3-dimensional force sensor. The friction coefficient was measured during actuation at the modulation frequency of $10 Hz$. (Fig.2b) confirms a reduction of approximately 45% for $48 V_{pp}$ that should be sufficient to produce a perceptible sensation.

4 Psychophysical experiment

A Psychophysical experiment was carried out on 12 volunteers aged 23 to 50. Figure 3a is an approximation of the psychophysical perception curve based on participants' responses to stimuli of varying intensity for modulations frequency of 25, 50 and 100 Hz . Secondly, participants were asked to associate each stimulus generated by the haptic interface with samples presenting different textures. Results are depicted in Figure 3b, each sample has a different characteristic length and is associated with a specific

frequency domain. Domain of sample B overlaps with the other two, which could mean that there is confusion in the perception of stimuli that are too close in frequency. In comparison frequency domains A and C are almost entirely separate. These results are promising and mean that our system is capable of producing a variety of textural sensations.

Fig. 3: a) Approximation of the psychophysical curve from the results of the 12 participants. The 50% detection threshold is reached for 17.2 V_{pp} . 100% of participants were able to detect a stimulus for voltages superior to 40 V_{pp} ; b) Results of the second part of the psychophysical campaign, the medians for each sample are respectively : 31.5 Hz, 71.7 Hz and 211 Hz

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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